

Reactor Antineutrino Oscillations and Geoneutrinos in SNO+

Will Parker on behalf of the SNO+ Collaboration

SNO+ The SNO+ Experiment

- ▶ **2 km** underground at **SNOLAB**, Canada
- ▶ Reuses the **SNO** infrastructure with major upgrades:
 - ▶ New calibration systems
 - ▶ Upgraded DAQ and electronics
 - ▶ New hold-down ropes
 - ▶ Scintillator plant + tellurium synthesis and purification

~9300 PMTs

18 m diameter PMT support structure

~2.5 m ultra pure water shielding between PMTs and AV

12 m diameter Acrylic Vessel

780 t liquid scintillator to be loaded with ^{130}Te for $0\nu\beta\beta$

More info in: JINST 16 P08059 (2021) <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-0221/16/08/P08059>

Search for $0\nu\beta\beta$ in ^{130}Te

Solar Neutrinos

Reactor Antineutrinos

Geoneutrinos

Supernova Neutrinos

Invisible Nucleon Decay

Water Phase

2017-2019

905t Ultra Pure Water

Partial Fill Phase

Mar-Oct 2020

320 t (47%) scintillator

Full Fill Phase

2022 - Present

Fully filled with ~780 t scintillator

Tellurium Phase

2026

0.5% loading of tellurium initially

- ▶ *Calibrations*
- ▶ *External background measurements*
- ▶ Solar Neutrinos
- ▶ Invisible Nucleon Decay
- ▶ Reactor Antineutrinos

- ▶ *Scintillator background measurements*
- ▶ Reactor Antineutrinos
- ▶ Direction Reconstruction

- ▶ *Characterisation of scintillator*
- ▶ *Scintillator background measurements*
- ▶ Reactor and geoneutrinos
- ▶ Solar, supernova neutrinos

- ▶ $0\nu\beta\beta$ searches!
- ▶ Reactor, geo, solar and supernova neutrino analyses will continue

- ▶ Nuclear reactors produce $\bar{\nu}_e$ via β decays
- ▶ ~ 6 $\bar{\nu}_e$ produced per fission
- ▶ Emitted neutrino energies $\lesssim 8$ MeV
- ▶ Dominant contributions from:
 ^{235}U , ^{238}U , ^{239}Pu , ^{241}Pu
- ▶ $\sim 5\%$ of fission energy is carried by $\bar{\nu}_e$
- ▶ Precise emitted spectrum depends on reactor type, fuel burn-up, maintenance schedule etc.

- ▶ **60%** of flux comes from three reactor complexes in Ontario, with baselines **240-350 km**
 - ▶ Remaining flux from ~ 100 cores in the USA
- ▶ Long baselines produce oscillation-driven spectral distortions
- ▶ Allows a measurement of neutrino oscillation parameters Δm_{21}^2 and θ_{12}
- ▶ Current **1.5 σ tension** between global solar and reactor measurements of Δm_{21}^2

Antineutrinos inverse β -decay on hydrogen nuclei in the scintillator, producing a neutron and a positron

The neutron thermalises and captures on a proton

The positron annihilates promptly

This coincidence signature is very powerful for rejecting backgrounds

- ▶ **Radioactive decays** in the Earth's crust and mantle produce $\bar{\nu}_e$ (geoneutrinos)
- ▶ Geoneutrinos are detected via **Inverse Beta Decays (IBD)**, giving identical signatures to reactor events
 - ▶ Separation from reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ relies on **spectral fits**
- ▶ Only decays from ^{238}U and ^{232}Th produce $\bar{\nu}_e$ above the IBD threshold
- ▶ The predicted flux has large uncertainties dominated by **local geology** and Earth-model variations
- ▶ Geoneutrinos provide a direct probe of **radiogenic heat production** in the Earth requiring measurements at **multiple global locations**
- ▶ **SNO+ made the first geoneutrino measurement in the Western Hemisphere**

- ▶ **Dominant background** to antineutrino IBDs
- ▶ α particles from ^{210}Po decays in the detector medium capture on ^{13}C in the scintillator
- ▶ This **mimics the IBD coincidence signal**
- ▶ Three possible **prompt** channels:
 - ▶ **Neutron recoils on protons**
 - ▶ **Neutron scatters inelastically on ^{12}C**
 - ▶ **Excited ^{16}O production followed by de-excitation gammas**

Figures from: <https://repository.upenn.edu/handle/20.500.14332/60242>

- ▶ (α, n) prompt events deposit energy over a **longer timescale** than IBD prompt events
- ▶ **Scintillation timing** is also different for β s (IBD) and protons (α, n)
 - ▶ β timing calibrated using in-situ ^{214}Bi and ^{214}Po decay pairs
 - ▶ Proton timing may be calibrated with ^{241}Am - ^9Be source
- ▶ Results in a different pulse shape that can be used to distinguish (α, n) from IBD events

Time residual is
time of flight
corrected hit time

$$t_{\text{res}} = t_{\text{hit}} - t.o.f - t_{\text{event}}$$

Pre-Classifier

SNO+ Impact of the (α, n) Classifier

Pre-Classifier

With Classifier

246 tagged coincidences in 685 days livetime

arxiv.org/abs/2511.11856

SNO+ only fit,
without (α, n)
classifier

Fit with PDG constraints
on oscillation parameters,
without (α, n) classifier

Fit with PDG constraints
on oscillation parameters,
with (α, n) classifier

	Expected	Fit	Fit (con.)	Fit (α, n) cut
Reactor IBD	140 ± 6	120 ± 5	136 ± 6	130^{+6}_{-5}
Geo ^{238}U IBD	29	38^{+15}_{-14}	38^{+15}_{-14}	27^{+8}_{-7}
Geo ^{232}Th IBD	8	11 ± 5	12^{+6}_{-5}	8^{+2}_{-3}
(α, n) p -scatters	80 ± 24	63 ± 19	58^{+20}_{-19}	22 ± 6
(α, n) other	12 ± 10	7 ± 5	7 ± 5	7 ± 4
α - p	7 ± 6	4^{+6}_{-4}	3^{+6}_{-3}	3^{+6}_{-3}
Atmospheric ν	4 ± 3	6^{+3}_{-2}	6 ± 3	5 ± 2
Sum	281	249	259	202
Observed	246	246	246	185

	Fit	Fit (con.)	Fit (α, n) cut
Δm_{21}^2 [$\times 10^{-5} \text{eV}^2$]	$7.93^{+0.21}_{-0.24}$	7.63 ± 0.17	7.56 ± 0.17
$\sin^2 \theta_{12}$	0.505 ± 0.134	0.310 ± 0.012	0.311 ± 0.012
Geo- $\bar{\nu}$ [TNU]	60^{+23}_{-22}	61^{+23}_{-22}	49^{+13}_{-12}
Geo- $\bar{\nu}$ U/Th	$3.38^{+1.39}_{-1.41}$	$3.30^{+1.41}_{-1.44}$	$3.29^{+1.42}_{-1.48}$

- ▶ $\Delta m_{21}^2 = (7.56 \pm 0.17) \times 10^{-5} \text{eV}^2$ $\sin^2 \theta_{12} = 0.311 \pm 0.012$ with **685 days livetime** of data
- ▶ Consistent with other long-baseline reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ measurements of Δm_{21}^2
- ▶ Measured geoneutrino flux $\phi = 49^{+13}_{-12}$ TNU consistent with global expectations

- ▶ Current measurement is for nearly 2 years livetime
- ▶ With increased data SNO+ sensitivity to Δm_{21}^2 will improve significantly
- ▶ (α, n) classifier **drastically reduces impact** of (α, n) events on Geoneutrino flux and Δm_{21}^2 measurements

- ▶ Reactor $\bar{\nu}_e$ oscillations measured over a long baseline at SNO+
- ▶ Δm_{21}^2 , $\sin^2\theta_{12}$, and geoneutrino flux measurements consistent with global data
- ▶ **Second experiment to measure Δm_{21}^2 from reactor antineutrinos**
- ▶ **First measurement of geoneutrino flux in the Western Hemisphere**
- ▶ Spectral fits provide constraints on (α, n) backgrounds, informing future low-energy $\bar{\nu}_e$ analyses
- ▶ Identification of (α, p) interactions as a non-negligible background in large liquid-scintillator experiments
- ▶ Precision will improve with **more data!**
 - ▶ Antineutrino analyses will continue through the tellurium phase

Backups

- ▶ PPO + bisMSB datasets: 245.78 + 439.14 days livetime
- ▶ 1D PDFs in reconstructed prompt energy
- ▶ Simultaneously fit signal and background PDF normalisations with systematic uncertainty and oscillation parameters
- ▶ Nominal prediction with $\sin^2\theta_{12} = 0.307$ and $\Delta m_{21}^2 = 7.50 \times 10^{-5} \text{eV}^2$
- ▶ Not including accidentals PDF as so low rate (0.35)

Event Selection

Cut	Prompt Event	Delayed Event
Valid Fit	True	True
Data Cleaning	Pass	Pass
Radius	< 5.7 m	< 5.7 m
Energy	0.9 - 8.0 MeV	1.85 - 2.5 MeV
Δt		< 2 ms
ΔR		< 2.5 m
Other Selection Criteria		
$^{214}\text{BiPo}$ Tag	False	False
Muon Veto		20 s
3000 Nhits Veto		1 s
Muon Spallation Cut		10 μs
Multiplicity Cut		$\mathcal{M} = 1$
Accidental Cut	$\mathcal{P} > -2.9$ (PPO)	-5.4 (bis-MSB)
(α, n) Classifier Cut	$\mathcal{F} > -10.20$ (PPO)	-7.23 (bis-MSB)

PDFs

	PPO		bisMSB	
	Nominal	Prior Uncertainty	Nominal	Prior Uncertainty
Reactor Nu (unoscillated)	89.72	3.89	165.11	7.17
Geo U	10.44	Geo U:Th = 3.7 ± 1.3	18.90	Geo U:Th = 3.7 ± 1.3
Geo Th	2.75	Geo U:Th = 3.7 ± 1.3	5.01	Geo U:Th = 3.7 ± 1.3
P. Recoil (Alpha, n)	31.17	9.35	53.78	16.13
C. Scatter (Alpha, n)	0.92	0.28	1.56	0.47
O. Excited (Alpha, n)	3.43	3.43	5.86	5.86
BiPo-like	2.86	2.38	4.60	3.48
Atmospheric	1.58	1.07	2.89	1.96

Systematics

	PPO			bisMSB		
	Nominal	Prior Uncertainty	Events Applied to	Nominal	Prior Uncertainty	Events Applied to
Energy Scale	1.0	0.011	All	1.0	0.01	All
Birk's Constant	0.074	0.004	All	0.074	0.004	All
Energy Convolution	0.00	4.9% * sqrt(E)	All	0.00	4.9% * sqrt(E)	All
(Alpha, n) P. R Energy Scale	1.0	0.03	Proton Recoil (Alpha, n)	1.0	0.03	Proton Recoil (Alpha, n)

SNO+ Liquid Scintillator Cocktail

Primary Fluor:

2.2 g/l concentration
Avoid self-absorption in LAB
Improves light yield

Double Beta Isotope:

High natural abundance
Affordable and scalable
Q value 2.527 MeV
TeDiol soluble in LAB

Anti Oxidant:

Improves stability
Improves optical purity

LAB + PPO + bis-MSB + Te-ButaneDiol + BHT + DDA

Scintillator:

High light yield
Good transparency
Compatible with Acrylic
Affordable

Secondary Fluor:

Shifts wavelength to PMT peak efficiency
Reduces self-absorption
Intrinsic light yield unaffected

Amine:

Improves stability
Increases light yield

▶ **Geoneutrinos**

- ▶ Antineutrinos from radioactivity in the Earth's crust
- ▶ Detected via **inverse beta decays**, identical in signature to reactor events

▶ **(α, n) Interactions**

- ▶ α -particles from radioactive decays in the detector materials capture on ^{13}C in the liquid scintillator
- ▶ Causes prompt and delay signals, mimicking the IBD coincidences

▶ **Atmospherics**

- ▶ Cosmic ray interactions in Earth's atmosphere produce antineutrinos which interact in the detector

- ▶ Pulse shapes also correlated with **energy** and **radial position**, in different ways for β s and protons
- ▶ Likelihood ratio would not capture this with PDFs averaged over E and R
- ▶ Instead use **Fisher Discriminant**
 - ▶ Finds projection vector that best separates (α, n) from IBDs
- ▶ Tune on (α, n) and IBD simulation

SNO+ ^{130}Te for $0\nu\beta\beta$ Searches

- ▶ High natural abundance (34%) -> no enrichment needed
- ▶ High Q-value (2.53 MeV), above most natural radioactivity
- ▶ Affordable, scalable, and chemically compatible with scintillator
- ▶ **Enables a large isotope mass in an ultra-low background detector**

Data from <https://doi.org/10.1088/1742-6596/598/1/012008>

All background components are within target levels, enabling world-leading sensitivity to $0\nu\beta\beta$ in ^{130}Te

ROI: 2.42 - 2.56 MeV $[-0.5\sigma - 1.5\sigma]$
 Counts/Year: 9.68

Projected 3-year sensitivity (0.5% natTe loading):

$$T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 2 \times 10^{26} \text{ yr, corresponding to a } m_{\beta\beta} = 31-143 \text{ meV}$$

- ▶ Next phase: increased **1.5%** **natural Te loading**, maintaining optical performance and stability

- ▶ Expected 5-year exposure ->

$$T_{1/2}^{0\nu} > 7.4 \times 10^{26} \text{ yr}$$

- ▶ Sensitivity extends well **into the inverted-ordering band** of $m_{\beta\beta}$

$$\left(T_{1/2}^{0\nu}\right)^{-1} = \langle m_{\beta\beta} \rangle^2 \times |M_{0\nu}|^2 \times G_{0\nu} \quad \langle m_{\beta\beta} \rangle = \left| \sum_i m_i U_{ei}^2 \right|$$